

RESOURCE-SAVING MELON PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY

Bibipatyma Yerenova

*Department of Technology and Food Safety
Kazakh National Agrarian Research University
8 Abai ave., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan, 050010*

Yevgeniy Medvedkov

Faculty of Distance Education¹

Dinara Tlevlessova✉

*Department of Food Technology¹
tlevlessova@gmail.com*

Ainura Kairbayeva

Department of Mechanization and Automation of Production Processes¹

¹*Almaty Technological University
100 Tole bi str., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan, 050012*

✉ **Corresponding author**

Abstract

The object of the study is the fruits of melon. The problem is the crop that remains in the fields. The article provides an overview of technologies for the processing of melons, and studies of the authors are given. On the basis of these studies, technological schemes for the production and formulation of such products as jam, jam, confiture, blended juices, vegetable oil from melon seeds were proposed and justified. Optimal additives and ways of introducing pectin into them are determined. The presence in finished products of vitamins of group B, vitamin C, β -carotene, almost all essential amino acids, micro- and macroelements, the content of which does not noticeably decrease during storage under the optimal conditions established by us. Studies have been carried out on the selection of an extractant and the determination of the optimal parameters for extraction, isolation, neutralization and drying of pectin from melon peel. As a result, pectin was obtained with a degree of esterification of 67..69 %, a jelly-forming ability of more than 170 degrees of Tarr Baker, and a jelly strength of about 460 mm Hg.

Keywords: melon, juice, jam, pectin, melon oil, extraction, precipitation, jelly, processing.

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1. Introduction

Food is the source of a complex of substances necessary for the body with a guarantee of complete safety. In this connection, the solution of the food problem requires a fundamentally new approach to resource use. It is necessary to carry out a comprehensive study of all potential sources of food, especially little studied and little-known. At the same time, the establishment of their chemical composition, nutritional and biological value, as well as the influence of seasonal factors, technological processing processes and the establishment of possible medicinal properties of these products is topical.

Along with increasing the production of products from raw materials of plant origin, in particular fruits and vegetables, the satisfaction of demand should be ensured through their rational use. It is necessary to improve the quality of products, eliminate its losses at all stages of production, transportation, storage and sale, broaden the introduction of non-waste production technologies, and improve product storage.

Melon crops, in particular melons, are the source of a number of substances necessary for the human body, especially vitamins, carbohydrates and minerals. Their cultivation is not very labor intensive.

Dietary and medicinal qualities of melon are very high. Their use in food contributes to the improvement of the body, the removal of toxins and cholesterol, helps in the treatment of disorders in the work of the gastrointestinal tract, urinary and cardiovascular systems, normalizes metabolism. Melon is valued for the high content of valuable easily digestible carbohydrates and proteins, as well as mineral salts. The oil, obtained from melon seeds, has medicinal abilities, known for a long time in folk medicine of the East.

By intensive melon processing it is possible to obtain juices, drinks, jams and other high-quality products with the addition of natural fruits and berries, which will be in high demand.

In addition, seeds of melon contain oil, which can be used in cosmetics, both alone and as part of complex products, including creams. Based on melon oil, you can prepare dietary supplements. Currently, melon seeds are used only as a planting material, while pulp and crusts are often waste when they are produced, at best the pulp is hand-dried and the crusts are used as animal feed. In the melon crust contains pectin, which is used in the food industry as a thickener and is part of the complexes used as dietary supplements.

Based on the above, we have set ourselves the actual goal of creating an integrated melon fruit processing technology using modern efficient technologies for obtaining food products with a balanced chemical composition, pectin and oil, which are functional products. World's largest producer of melons, accounted for over 52 % production by weight. In the past, melons considered to be a 'seasonal delight' because of their limited availability throughout the year, however, for production flexibility, imports availability and popularity, melons are now available in year-round. In recent, the melon production is 20 % within total fruits production worldwide. Over the next three decades, a forty percent increase in the production of melons is required for a growing population.

The inherent complexities in achieving this unparalleled increase in the demands of melon fruits are worsen by the yield-depressing consequences of climate alterations or dissimilarities. With declining agricultural land and water resources, and assailing microbes and pests, the expected increases in the melons production cannot be reached at an efficient level. Elite varieties of melons such as, tolerance to drought condition and inferior lands, or disease resistant that can yield more with fewer inputs will be pivotal to success. Moreover, varieties of melons can improve with the traits such as, seedless, good shelf life, excellent flesh color and good shapes that will make them more attractive to consumers. Plant breeding methods (conventional or molecular breeding) have to be applied for regenerate the elite varieties in melon fruits to meet the global demand for next decades. This paper highlights some of the scientific and technological tools that ought to be the necessary for all improvement programs of the melon production [1].

In order to design equipment and facilities for drying, preservation and processing of muskmelon. The knowledge of its thermal properties is very essential. Therefore in study Syed Shabuddin et al the effective thermal conductivity of Muskmelon (*Cucumis melo*) cultivator Ballari area, Karnataka, India were analyzed by Transient line heat source method at different moisture content (40 % to 90 %) wb for two different densities. The analysis reveals that the thermal conductivity of Musk melon increased with increase in Moisture content in the range of 0.4403 W/m°C & 0.5955 W/m°C. The Experimental values obtained were statistically analyzed & compared with Sweat & Anderson equations. These values were found in good agreement with the predicted models. The analyzed data will help to develop preservation techniques, enhance shelf life and better control on both process and product of food industry and researchers [2].

Moisture, ash, fat, protein, trace and heavy metals and fatty acid profiles were determined using AOAC methods. Melon seeds examined were found to contain moisture (3.89±0.80 %), fat (48.92±0.9 %), ash (3.22±0.50 %) and protein (30.16±0.98 %). The trace metals found in the melon seeds were potassium (1,042 mg/kg), magnesium (742.45 mg/kg), calcium (136 mg/kg), manganese (40.87 mg/kg), iron (19.31 mg/kg), sodium (12.85 mg/kg) and selenium (0.11 mg/kg). Heavy metals: lead (0.047 mg/kg), cadmium (0.0053 mg/kg), mercury (0.006 mg/kg) and arsenic (0.093 mg/kg) were found in melon seeds. Melon seeds had 11 fatty acids among which are palmitic, stearic, oleic, linoleic and linolenic acid, the most abundant being linoleic acid (58.35–64.89 %). The oil of melon seed was found to be high in unsaturated fatty acid (84.34 %) [3].

Cucumis melo var. in odors seeds were found to contain 4.5 % moisture, 25.0 % crude fat, 25.0 % crude protein, 23.3 % crude fiber, 2.4 % ash and 19.8 % carbohydrate. The iodine and saponification values, and unsaponifiable matter and free fatty acid contents of freshly extracted honeydew melon seed oil were 153.4 g I₂/100 g oil, 210.2 mg KOH/g oil, 0.9 and 2.5 %, respectively. The oil had a color index of 1.6Y+0.4R, and had 10 fatty acids, of which 86.1 % were unsaturated. Linoleic acid predominated with 69.0 % followed by oleic acid (16.8 %) and palmitic acid (8.4 %). LLL (24.9 %), OLL (21.5 %), PLL (15.9 %) and POL (12.4 %) (where L, O, P and S denote linoleic, oleic, palmitic and stearic acids, respectively) were the major triacylglycerols present. The melting and crystallization temperatures were -5.12 °C and -59.01 °C, respectively. Electronic nose analysis showed the presence of more volatile compounds compared to refined sunflower oil, an oil rich also in linoleic acid [4].

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Also, the reason for the rare use of melon seeds is the lack of equipment for processing melon seeds. Mechanically driven melon seed husking machine was designed, manufactured and tested. The machine consists of a loading hopper, a peeling unit, a receiving chute, a feed system and a bed. Peeling was carried out according to the principle of a rotor, which, under the action of centrifugal force, threw melon seeds onto a peeling drum, and then the seeds were collected on a rotating disk with blades that create an impact force to remove the kernel from the shell. The tests carried out showed that the effectiveness of the shelling of the machine increased with increasing humidity and speed. The maximum peeling efficiency percentage of 95 % was obtained at a seed moisture content of 26.6 % db and a peeling speed of 2190 rpm. It has been found that the percentage of seed damage decreases with increasing seed moisture. The machine capacity and throughput were 192 kg/h and 796 kg/h, respectively [6].

The sheller consists of a hopper that contains raw melon seeds and opens directly into the shelling chamber. The peeling chamber consists of a disk and a rotor. The inside of the chamber is lined with tiny metal rods to give it a rough surface. Flat metal rods are welded around the deck (rotor) at an angle of 45°. The concave is attached directly to a 2 horsepower electric motor which rotates it counterclockwise to clean the melon seeds. The peeled melon seeds and cotyledons go directly to the cleaning chamber, where the installed fan blows off the chaff, and the cotyledons are collected directly through the opening under the cleaning chamber. The sink is built from improvised materials, and its operation does not require special skills. The tests were carried out at speeds of 750, 950, 1200 rpm and humidity of 7 % and 10 % (WB). The results of the analysis showed that an increase in the speed of the peeling unit increases the shelling and stripping capabilities of the peeler. However, the breakage of shelled melon seeds also increases with the speed of the shelling unit. With an increase in the moisture content of melon seeds from 7 % to 10 %, there was a sharp decrease in the number of broken seeds from 95 % to 3 %. The dehulling capacity has been reduced from 148 kg/h to 145 kg/h at a concave speed of 1200 rpm, the cleaning capacity has also been reduced from 52 kg/h to 39 kg/h at a concave speed of 750 rpm. It can be concluded that the peeling of melon seeds is unacceptable at a moisture content of less than 10 % and the peeling speed should be about 950 rpm. The sheller efficiency is about 90 % [7]. A machine for sorting and grading seeds was also developed [8]. A melon seed extractor has been proposed. The evaluation of the prototype was carried out based on cleaning efficiency, extraction efficiency, machine performance, power consumption, damaged seeds and operating costs. The prototype was evaluated at four different feed rates (20, 30, 40 and 50 kg/min), five drum speeds (3.25, 5.47, 6.98, 8.52 and 10.64 m/s) and four time intervals (0, 3, 6 and 9 days). The results showed that an increase in the speed of the crushing drum, a period of sowing melon seeds and a decrease in the feed rate tend to reduce the cleaning efficiency, where the maximum value of the cleaning efficiency was 88.83 % at a crushing drum speed of 10.64 m/s, a feed rate of 20 kg/min and

sowing time for melon seeds 9 days after harvest [9]. An oil press for melon seeds was developed, an analysis was carried out and a conclusion was obtained when obtaining oil from melon seeds, the husk lowers the quality of the oil, without the husk the amount of oil decreases. 10 % of husks is chosen as a rational condition for squeezing oil by cold pressing [10].

2. Materials and methods

During the research work, traditional methods of chemical, physicochemical and microbiological, organoleptic analysis and determination of the physical and mechanical properties of products, methods of mathematical processing of the received materials, including using the standard computer program Excel, were used.

The converting fraction was subjected to thermal treatment by IR irradiation with a surface temperature of 85 °C to 95 °C and a final moisture content of 4.0 % to 5.0 %. To achieve these temperature parameters and the specified final moisture content of the melon seeds, it is advisable to perform IR irradiation at temperatures from 65 °C to 100 °C for seeds with an initial moisture content of 6.3 % to 9.9 %. At the same time, the specific heat flux should be maintained at 900 W/m², and the distance between the IR lamps and the layer in one seed should be 90 mm.

Micronized melon seeds were crushed by the single impact method in a centrifugal handle at a rotational speed of 1500 rpm and load on incoming melon seeds from 160 kg per hour to 170 kg per hour. The resulting hulled contains from 25.0 % to 27.0 % of a free fruit shell and about 25.0 % of a unhulled with an underarm.

Hulled was divided on a sieve surface with a hole diameter of 2 mm for preliminary removal of oilseed dust. Then, the run fraction was separated on sieves with a hole diameter of 3, 4 and 5 mm. Unhulled and unde-hulled were taken for control.

The core fraction containing 8 % of the fruit shell was fed to heat treatment. Heat treatment of the core fraction of melon seeds by IR irradiation was carried out to a temperature of 700 °C.

The micronized oil material was pressed on a DoLong company press with a 6 mm diameter die at a rotational speed of 40 rpm.

On the control site, the unhulled and unde-hulled fraction was divided into a core fraction, which was fed to heat treatment by IR irradiation together with the main stream of the core fraction, and to the unhulled and unde-hulled, taken for crushing into the centrifugal handle. The resulting hulled was removed to the aero separator, where it was divided into a core fraction that was diverted to the total core fraction before the heat treatment, and to a free fruit shell, which was sent to control the free fruit shell.

In the control area of the free fruit shell, it was separated on the screen surface and in a vertical air flow. The separated particles of the core were taken to the total flow of the core fraction before heat treatment, and the free fruit shell was removed from production. It can be used as biofuel for the boiler house.

When studying the seeds of melons, their linear dimensions were studied, the mass of 1000 seeds. The arithmetic mean of the three parallel measurements was taken as the average measurement. Determination of the component and fractional composition of hulled melon seeds were carried out by the generally accepted methods in fat and oil industry. Their fatty acid composition was determined by gas-liquid chromatography from methyl esters. The quantitative calculation of the fatty acid content was calculated from the area of the peaks on chromatograms. Determination of the mass fraction of protein in melon seeds was performed according to the Kjeldahl method in accordance with the requirements. The amino acid composition of the proteins was studied chromatographically using an automatic analyzer Kapel-103. The content of the protein fractional composition was performed by Osborn's method. The mass fraction of cellulose in melon seeds was found according to the generally accepted method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physico-mechanical and chemical characteristics of melon fruit

Characteristics of the main types of melon sold in the Almaty region, indicating the varietal belonging to the use for processing are detailed in the intermediate report 2015 [6].

3. 1. 1. Geometric characteristics of melon fruits, the mass of the constituent parts of the fruit

A great importance for determining the finished melon products is the ratio of the fruit parts: flesh, crust, seeds and placenta. To determine this indicator, were used fruits with previously measured linear dimensions. Fruits were cut into slices and peel the crust 5–10 mm thick, depending on the variety. The same-name constituents of fruits of the same variety were combined and weighed on an electronic balance with an accuracy of 1 gram. The data obtained are shown in Tables 1, 2.

Table 1
Finished measure of melon fruits

Type	Fruit mass, g	Flesh		Crust		Placenta		Seeds	
		g	%	g	%	g	%	g	%
Iliyskaya	1,210	765	63.22	360	29.75	46	3.8	39	3.22
Myrzachulskaya	5,575	4,000	71.75	1,370	24.57	133	2.39	72	1.29
Kolkhoznytsa	1,150	793	68.96	290	25.22	42	3.65	25	2.17
Gurbek	4,225	2,645	62.6	1,320	31.24	210	4.97	50	1.18
Ameri	3,200	1,800	53.13	1,060	33.13	240	10.6	100	3.13
Inzhirnaya	3,460	1,890	54.62	1,210	34.97	270	7.8	90	2.6
Gulyabi	4,175	2,645	63.35	1,320	31.62	135	3.23	75	1.8
Zhyldyz	1,990	1,310	65.83	570	28.64	67	3.37	43	2.16

According to the table finished amount of flesh varies from 53.13 to 71.75 % for different kinds of melons, the highest for Myrzachulskaya melon, and the lowest for Ameri. The thickest crusts of Inzhirnaya, Ameri, Gulyabi and Gurbek, respectively, 34.97 %, 33.13 %, 31.62 % and 31.24 %. Basically, these are melons of latest and medium-maturity varieties. A larger amount of crust makes them more preferable for the production of pectin.

The content of seeds varies from 1.18 to 3.22 %. Dependence of the content of seeds on what class to maturity dates includes melons are not observed. This indicator depends only on the characteristics of the variety.

Table 2
Characteristic parameters of melon

Melon types	Shape index
Iliyskaya	0.92–0.96, medium 0.94
Myrzachulskaya	1.80–1.90, medium 1.85
Kolkhoznytsa	0.96–1.00, medium 0.98
Gurbek	1.20–1.25, medium 1.23
Ameri	2.26–2.4, medium 2.33
SaryGulyabi	1.55–1.60, medium 1.57
Zhyldyz	1.20–1.25, medium 1.23
Inzhirnaya	0.90–0.95, medium 0.94

Analysis of tabulated data indicates that the shape index of various kinds of melons varies widely: from 0.9 in Inzhirnaya to 2.4 in Ameri. The shape index is more important while choosing devices for removing crust from melon fruits. The higher the shape index, the easier it is to mechanize the process of peeling it [29, 30].

3. 1. 2. Density of melon pulp

In the framework of the conducted studies in 2015, the results were obtained for determining the density of the layer adjacent to the crust and inner part of melons of various varieties, which are given in Table 3. The results of experimental data indicate that the melon density throughout

the fetal volume is not the same and its decrease from adjacent to the peel layers to the inner (in the center).

Table 3
Density of melon flesh

Melon layer	Density of melon flesh, $\rho \cdot 10^{-3}$, kg/m ³						
	Type «Iliyskaya»	Type «Gurbek»	Type «Ameri»	Type «Myrzachulskaya»	Type «Gulyabi»	Type «Inzhir-naya»	Type «Zhyldyz»
Adjacent	1.26	1.28	1.24	1.29	1.30	1.32	1.30
Middle	1.12	1.13	1.15	1.18	1.21	1.23	1.19
Inner	1.10	1.11	1.12	1.14	1.14	1.16	1.15

3. 1. 3. Adhesive abilities of melon flesh

The adhesion abilities of melon pulp, in particular the stickiness of melons of various varieties, were determined on the device by a CT-2 structurometer, the experimental data are given in **Table 4**.

Table 4
Determination of adhesion abilities of melon flesh

Index	Melon types/ layers						
	Early ripening		Medium ripening			Late ripening	
	Saryzhambylsha	Kizylzhambylsha	Boskauyn	Karagurbek	Gulyabigreen	Gulyabiorange	Kizylgulyabi
Adhesion pressure, N/m ²	2.4–2.6	2.3–2.6	2.8–3.0	2.6–2.9	2.9–3.1	3.0–3.2	3.1–3.2

The obtained data indicate that the adhesion stress of all kinds of melons lies in the range of 2.6 to 3.2 N/m², and for specimens of the same variety, the fluctuations are much less, and for the medium-ripening varieties it is 2.6 to 3.0 on average, for late ripening – 2,9–3,2 N/m².

3. 1. 4. Frictional abilities of melons (coefficient of friction)

The data of the experimental studies on the determination of the coefficient of friction are presented in **Table 5**.

The results of these studies indicate that with increasing thickness of the peel with an adjacent layer of pulp, the coefficient of external friction decreases. Based on the results of the experimental data given in **Table 5**, a graph of the dependence of the coefficient of external friction on the thickness of the melon skin is plotted (**Fig. 1**).

Analysis of the nature of the curves indicates the existence of a general pattern: a decrease in the coefficient of friction with an increase in the thickness of the skin, and a decrease are more significant in melons of mid-ripening and late-ripening varieties.

The linear model is most convenient for practical use. Mathematical processing of experimental data with the use of Excel tools allowed obtaining regression equations, which are shown in the diagram.

Since the obtained value $R > 0.9$, it is possible to say about a high accuracy of approximation [10–12].

Table 5
Dependence of melon friction coefficient on melon crust thickness

Crust thickness, mm	Melon types (average values)		
	Early ripening	Medium ripening	Late ripening
3	0.31	0.24	0.23
5	0.28	0.23	0.21
7	0.25	0.23	0.19
10	0.23	0.21	0.19

Fig. 1. Graph of the dependence between coefficient of friction and thickness of the crust of melon

3. 1. 5. Specific cutting force

Determination of the specific cutting force and physic – mechanical characteristics of materials under volume compression was carried out on a measuring complex based on the Structurometer-2 instrument, the results of which were recorded in a computer (Fig. 2, 3). The data was processed by Microsoft Office Excel.

The values of the specific cutting forces of the melon pulp layers adjacent to the crust were determined in the work, when the peel was separated from the pulp of some sorts of melons, combined in terms of ripening: early maturing, mid-ripening and late ripening.

Analyzing the given curves, which are characteristic for all varieties, can be concluded that in the initial period of contact between the knife and the crust, the elastoplastic deformation occurs with the crust. The cutting force in this case changes insignificantly, with the limiting value of the deformation, a sudden increase in the force occurs, which ends with the destruction of the material. At the same time while cutting the pulp, the cutting force remains practically constant when the knife moves inside the pulp.

The values of the specific cutting force for different types of melon and its averaged value are given in **Table 6**.

It can be seen from the table that the deviation from the average cutting force for individual varieties does not exceed the values (–7.20...+6.31) % for pulp and (–1.60...+2.50) % for the crust.

Fig. 2. Graph of the dependence of the cutting force on the movement of the knife while peeling the crust of the melon of the type Myrzachulskaya

Fig. 3. Graph of the dependence of the cutting force on the movement of the knife when cutting the melon flesh of the type Myrzachulskaya

Table 6

The Values of the specific cutting force for different types of melon

Type	Specific cutting force, N/m	
	Pulp	Ctust
Iliyskaya	225	2,418
Myrzachulskaya	206	2,386
Kolkhoznytsa	227	2,421
Gurbek	216	2,410
Ameri	236	2,479
SaryGulyabi	214	2,387
Zhyldyz	218	2,412
Inzhirnaya	234	2,485
Average	222	2,424.75
More deviation	+6.31 %	+2.50 %
Less deviation	-7.20 %	-1.60 %

Thus, the conducted studies allow to conclude that the average value of the specific cutting force for the studied melon varieties with an error not exceeding 7.2 % for pulp and 2.5 % for the peel can be used in engineering calculations for different varieties, with condition of using safety factor [14–17].

3. 1. 6. Efforts of puncturing the melon crust

Determination of the piercing force of the melon crust was carried out using a CT-2 structurometer. For the construction of graphs, a linear model is used, as the most convenient for practical applications.

The obtained dependences are the initial data for calculating the energy expenditure for puncturing the melon peel when determining the engine power for the installation. **Fig. 4** shows the dependence of the force of the crust destroying the crust of various kinds of melons by the lateral surface of indenters of different diameters. The results presented in **Fig. 4** show a directly proportional dependence of the fracture force on the diameter of the rod of the indenter. The degree of approximation R is close to 1, which indicates the applicability of the obtained dependences.

The next stage of our research was the building of non-linear regression of melon skin piercing process. Using the estimates of b -factors it is possible to record the following quadratic regression equations for two parameters of melon skin piercing: Y – force of melon skin piercing F , N .

$$Y = 10.07333 + 1.22767x_1 - 0.09300x_1^2 + 5.17933x_2 + 0.41800x_2^2 + 0.73200x_1x_2, \quad (1)$$

x_1 – pin sharpening angle, deg; x_2 – pin diameter, mm.

Fig. 4. Puncture force versus diameter for indenters with tip angle $\alpha=45^\circ$

3. 1. 7. Physical and mechanical characteristics for volumetric compression

After processing the results of the experiments, the elastoplastic properties of melon pulp of various varieties, in particular the Myrzachulskaya and Ameri varieties of the most common varieties were calculated. Analysis of the data made it possible to conclude that such indices as plasticity, softness, relative residual compression with an increase in the compression rate from 20 to 100 mm/min decrease slightly, and recoverability and bulk modulus of elasticity increase.

Graphs of the dependence of the change in the bulk modulus of elasticity on the compression rate for melons of the above varieties are given in Fig. 5. The dependence with a high degree of accuracy is described by the equations of the straight line, which are shown in the graphs, which also give the reliability values of the approximation. The values of which indicate a good correspondence of the equations to the experimental data.

According to the experimental data, the values of the effective viscosity and bulk modulus of elasticity for the melon pulp of various grades were calculated for different values of the compression rate. The equations describing this dependence, the reliability of the approximation and the deviation of the experimental values of these quantities from the calculated values are given in Table 7 [17, 18].

Table 7

Average values of effective viscosity and bulk modulus of mash melon of various grades at separation of 50 % juice-gravity

Index	Equation (v , m/s)	Reliability of the approximation	Deviation of average value
Effective viscosity, kPa	$2,086+6.767v$	0.97	(+5.3; -4.1) %
Bulk modulus of elasticity, kPa	$5,898+2.023v$	0.96	(+3.2; -2.2) %

Fig. 5. Graph of the dependence between bulk modulus and compression rate

3. 1. 8. Chemical composition of melon fruits

Research work was carried out in the accredited testing laboratory “Food safety” of the Almaty Technological University. Where the following indicators of melons of late-ripening varieties were determined: mass fraction of solids, protein mass fraction, mass fraction of fat, mass fraction of pectin substances, vitamin C content, carotenoids, potassium, magnesium, iron, organic acids and antioxidant activity, using modern standard research methods.

The chemical composition of melons of late-ripening varieties is presented in **Table 8**. The table confirms that the Myrzachulskaya melon variety is more balanced in composition, the vegetable protein content is almost 3.8 times higher in comparison with the Zhuldyz variety and 1.9 times with the Ameri type [18].

The Myrzachulskaya variety contains more fat – 0.26 %, which is 0.134 % higher than the Zhuldyz variety and 0.17 % higher than the Ameri variety. According to the content of the mass fraction of pectin substances, the Myrzachulskaya variety is inferior to the Zhuldyz grade by 0.11 g/100 g, but does not exceed the Ameri grade by 0.045/100 g.

The Myrzachulskaya grade for ascorbic acid, vitamin C content is 2.78 mg/100 g higher than that of Zhuldyz and 6.61 mg/100 g higher than that of Ameri variety.

The content of carotenoids is approximately at the same level, with a small lead the Zhuldyz variety, then the Myrzachulskaya and Ameri variety (0.12, 0.1124, 0.104 mg/100 g, respectively). Melons are rich in potassium, magnesium and iron, which are so necessary to maintain the tone of the cardiovascular system of the body.

These tables show that the best indicator is Ameri variety, it contains 117.38 mg/100 g of potassium, 10.846 mg/100 g of magnesium and 1.193 mg/100 g of iron. The second place is taken by the Myrzachulskaya variety – 116.64 mg/100 g of potassium, 10.812 mg of magnesium and 1.007 mg/100 g of iron. In the Zhuldyz variety, respectively, 113.0 mg/100 g of potassium, 10.43 mg/100 g of magnesium and significantly lower in iron content – only 0.353 mg/100 g.

In Ameri variety, the content of malic acid is 348.8 mg/kg, which is much higher than in the Zhuldyz strain at 47 mg/kg and at 58.8 mg/kg – the Myrzachulskaya variety.

According to the content of citric acid, the Zhuldyz variety is 47.5 mg/kg, then the Myrzachulskaya variety is 27.0 mg/kg and the Ameri grade is 18.0 mg/kg.

Table 8
Chemical composition of melons of late-ripening varieties

Indexes, values	Late ripening melon types		
	Zhuldyz	Myrzachulskaya	Ameri
Protein mass fraction, %	0.174	0.674	0.346
Fat mass fraction, %	0.126	0.26	0.09
Mass fraction of pectin substances g/100 g	0.53	0.42	0.375
Vitamin C, mg/100 g	13.97	16.75	10.14
Carotenoids, mg/100 g	0.12	0.1124	0.104
Potassium, mg/100 g	113.0	116.64	117.38
Magnesium, mg/100 g	10.43	10.812	10.846
Iron, mg/100 g	0.353	1.007	1.193
Antioxidant activity, mg/100 g	27.3	27.4	28.0
Organic acids:			
Succinic acid, mg/kg	56.2	62.0	6.3
Malic acid, mg/kg	301.8	290.0	348.8
Citric acid, mg/kg	47.5	27.0	18.0

Succinic acid is more abundant in the Myrzachulskaya variety, 62.0 mg/kg, less in the Ameri variety, only 6.3 mg/kg, and in the Zhuldyz grade of succinic acid 56.2 mg/kg.

The total antioxidant activity in the Ameri variety is 28 mg/100 g. In the Myrzachulskaya and Zhuldyz varieties, the level of antioxidant activity is practically the same, respectively 27.4 mg/100 g and 27.3 mg/100 g.

Thus, given the rich chemical composition of melons of late-ripening varieties, they should be used for the production of long-term storage products of increased food and biological value in order to expand the range of products from unconventional types of food raw materials with a high content of biologically active substances.

Caloric value was 34–36 kcal/100 g. Nutritional value, g/100 g: proteins 0.4–0.6; fats 0.24–0.35; carbohydrates 7.3–7.5; food fibers 0.8–1.0; water 88–92; unsaturated fatty acids – less than 0.1; saturated fatty acids – less than 0.1.

Chemical composition, respectively, for the varieties Kolkhoznitsa and Myrzachulskaya: water – 6.0–6.2; lipids – 25.0–26.5; protein ($N \times 6.25$) – 22.5–25.5; starch and soluble sugars – 10.0–11.0; pentosans – up to 8.0; cellulose – 21.4–20.0; ash – 3.0–2.5. The core contains up to 30–50 % of the oil, and in the husk – 0.5–0.6 %.

3. 1. 9. Content and structure of pectin in melon fruits

To study the content of pectin in melon fruits, the following types of melons were used in the Almaty region: Inzhirnaya (sample No. 1), Gulyabi (No. 2), Myrzachulskaya (No. 3), Gurbek (No. 4) and Ameri (No. 5).

The chemical analysis was carried out in the laboratory of the “Quality of Functional Food” by the Research Institute of Biotechnology of the Kuban State Agrarian University executors of the topic under the supervision of laboratory staff. For the analyzes, melons of the above varieties, brought from Almaty, were taken. The results of the determination of pectin substances are presented in **Table 9**. The results of the analysis showed that the moisture content in different parts of the melon is not the same. So the highest humidity was in the crust 88.6 %, and the smallest in the placenta 82.8. Moisture of the pulp was 82.8 %. The mass fraction of pectin substances on absolutely dry matter in the crust is 10.9 % more than 2 times higher than this figure in melon pulp 5.09 %. The relatively high content of total pectin in the placenta is 7.44 %, which makes it a potential target for the extraction of pectin, possibly in the form of industrial product – liquid pectin, for use on site for the production of jams or pectin-containing beverages [19].

The content of pectins in the raw product due to its high humidity does not exceed 1.28 % in the placenta and 1.18 % in the crust [20].

Table 9
Content of pectin substances in the melon of Myrzachulskaya variety

Index	Sample No. 3 – Myrzachulskaya		
	Crust	Placenta	Pulp
ppm. humidity, %	88.6	82.8	85.1
ppm pectin substances, %	1.18	1.28	0.77
Hydrate Pectin, %	0.26	0.15	0.22
Protopectin, %	0.98	1.13	0.55
ppm. pectin substances in terms of a.s.v, %	10.9	7.44	5.09
Hydrate Pectin, (a.s.v.), %	2.3	0.87	1.4
Protopectin, (a.v.), %	8.6	6.57	3.69
The proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances, %	78.90	88.31	72.50

An important indicator for the suitability of raw materials for processing for the production of pectin is the proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances. If the index is 70–90 %, then such raw material can be used to produce pectin. As can be seen from the table, the content of protopectin in all parts of the melon enters this interval, and in the placenta the proportion of protopectin is 88.31 %. In the crust, this indicator is in the middle of the interval – 78.90 %, which again confirms its suitability for extraction of pectin, taking into account its high yield during melon processing. The content of protopectin in the flesh is close to the lower boundary of the interval, which makes it unprofitable for pectin production, but it can be used for pectin-containing products.

A similar pattern is observed in studies of melons of the Gulyabitype, the results of which are presented in **Table 10**.

This melon is more juicy pulp, the moisture content in it reaches 90.3 %, and the crust is slightly drier – 87.7 %.

The mass fraction of the total pectin in the crust is 1.21 %, which, after recalculation to an absolutely dry substance, is 9.8 %, 1.1 % lower than that of the Myrzachulskaya type. The proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances in the crust is 82.65 %, which is higher than in Myrzachulskaya and makes it no less suitable for the production of pectin.

The results of melon crust analyzes of Ameri, Gurbek and Inzhirnaya sorts are given in **Table 11**. For these varieties, only the crust was examined as a more promising raw material.

The results given in **Table 11** show that the content of pectin in the crust of raw Inzhirnaya melon is the highest of all five samples – 1.67 % due to the lowest moisture content in it of 82.4 %, in absolutely dry matter of this melon pectin is also quite a lot of 9.5 %, which is not much inferior to the grade of Gulyabi. Very low content of pectin in the crust of Gurbek melon is 7.43 % and, especially, in the melon crust of Ameri 6.13 %. However, in the latter variety, practically all pectin is protopectin. The proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances is 96.25 %, which, taking into account its thick crust, the yield of which at cutting is 33.13 %, does not exclude the Amerisort from the raw material for the production of pectin.

Table 10
The content of pectin substances in the melon of the Gulyabi type

Index	Sample No. 2 – Gulyabi	
	Crust	Pulp
ppm. moisture content, %	87.7	90.3
ppm. pectin substances, %	1.21	0.8
Hydrate Pectin, %	0.21	0.2
Protopectin, %	1.0	0.6
ppm. pectin substances in terms of a.s.v, %	9.8	8.2
Hydrate-Pectin, (a.s.v.), %	1.7	2.0
Protopectin, (a.v.), %	8.1	6.2
The proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances, %	82.65	75.6

Table 11

The content of pectin substances in the crust of melons of different varieties

Index	Sample No. 1 Inzhirnaya	Sample No. 4 Gurbek	Sample No. 5 Ameri
	(crust)	(crust)	(crust)
ppm. moisture content, %	82.4	89.1	87.4
ppm. pectin substances, %	1.67	1.41	0.78
HydratePectin, %	0.37	0.2	0.029
Protopectin, %	1.3	1.21	0.75
ppm. pectin substances in terms of a.s.v, %	9.5	7.43	6.13
Hydrate-Pectin, (a.s.v.), %	2.1	1.83	0.23
Protopectin, (a.v.), %	7.4	5.6	5.9
The proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances, %	77.89	75.37	96.25

Research have also shown that in all types of material studied, pectins contain carboxyl groups esterified with methanol and do not contain carboxyl groups esterified with ammonia. According to the degree of esterification, the pectins contained in the melon, as in the pumpkin, are classified as low-esterified, unlike apple, which are highly esterified. This indicates a lower solubility in water of pectin melons compared to apple pectins.

According, pectins with an esterification degree of more than 66 % are highly soluble in water (for example, apple), and less than 39.6 % are slightly soluble. The degree of esterification of pectins of all sorts of melon is closer to the latter. Pectins with a low content of methoxyl groups contained in a melon are able to form jelly without sugar in the presence of a small amount of polyvalent metal ions. In the melon, a large content of acetyl groups associated with hydroxyl groups of pectin substances was found, which significantly worsens their nucleus-forming properties.

Usually in the confectionery industry for the production of jams and confitures use highly esterified pectin with a slow gelling (gelling starts at a lower temperature). For experiments used pectin produced by AndrePect (China) apple APA 105 highly esterified, very slow gelling.

To prepare dessert products, a melon of the Myrzachulskaya variety was used. For the preparation of jam, pieces of melon were passed through a chopper with holes of 5 mm, jams – cut the flesh into pieces of 10×(20...30)×(40...50) mm size, for jam a solid residue was used after separation of juice with a particle size of 0.1...1 mm. Pectin was added in an amount of 2...10 grams per kg of product. Before insertion into the product, to prevent the formation of lumps, pectin was either mixed with sugar in a ratio of 1:6 or an aqueous solution was prepared: one part of dry pectin is mixed with three parts of sugar and the resulting mixture was dissolved in 16 parts of water. For the formation of a jelly with the use of highly esterified pectins, it is necessary to create an acidic medium, so it is most expedient to add food citric acid (as a 50 % aqueous solution), as determined in an amount that provides a pH of 2.7...2.8. The content of solids to obtain the optimal jelly is 60–70 % (determined by a refractometer). As a result, it was found that the optimal amount of pectin for confiture was about 10 g/kg, jam 8 g/kg, jam 5 g/kg product. Such a dosage of pectin made it possible to obtain the necessary viscous consistency of the product. The strength of the jelly was 455...490 N/mm².

Organoleptic indices were determined by 6 independent experts, including representatives of the canning plant of SD and Co LLP (Zarechny village, Almaty region). The evaluation was carried out on a 5-point scale. As test subjects, consistency, color, odor, taste, smell (flavor) were adopted. The results of the evaluation are given in **Table 12**.

In all the samples, pectin was added, with the exception of the seventh, in which starch was added. Organoleptic indices of melon products indicate that they are a homogenous ground mass from pale yellow to light orange-brown color, without delamination, with a pleasant sweet melon taste, characteristic of the melon fruit aroma and jelly-like consistency. The jam contains pieces of melon that have retained their shape. In general, all samples of products were highly appreciated and were recommended for production. Acts of tasting are given in Attachment D. Tasting and

interviews of performers on melon products and their perspective on the market were shown by the Khabar agency on television.

Table 12

Tasting results

Product	Appearance	Color	Smell (aroma)	Taste	Consistent	General impression	Overall-rating
Jam with raspberry juice	5.0	5.0	5.0	4.83	4.83	5.0	4.94
Pure jam	4.83	5.0	4.83	5.0	4.67	5.0	4.89
Three-fold cooking jam	4.67	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.5	5.0	4.78
Yellow color jam with orange flavor	4.83	5.0	4.5	4.83	4.5	4.83	4.75
Confiture	4.83	4.66	4.5	4.67	5.0	4.83	4.75
Orange color jam with orange flavor	4.83	4.83	4.67	4.33	4.83	4.83	4.72
Jam with strach	4.67	4.83	4.67	4.5	4.33	4.5	4.58

Studies of food and biological values of products are determined by chemical analysis using standard methods. The results for the tested products are given in **Table 13**. In addition, in the samples of jam and confiture, the content of essential and conditionally indispensable amino acids is noted, % mass: lysine – 0.03; tyrosine – 0.02; phenylalanine – 0.02; histidine – 0.02; leucine+isoleucine – 0.02; methionine – 0.01; valine – 0.06; threonine – 0.27; alanine – 0.29.

Table 13

Food and biological value of melon products

Indicators	Name of material and product				
	Jam	Jam	Jam (povidlo)	Jam (Varennye)	Confiture
Dry substances, %	72.55	41.42	69.02	79.02	54.8
Sugar, %	72.8	40.3	61.0	68.3	48
Proteins, %	0.50	0.28	0.47	0.54	0.38
Vitamins, mg/100 g					
B ₁	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.03
B ₂	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
C	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
β-carotene	5.1	2.9	4.87	5.61	3.9
Antioxidant activity, mg/100 g	17.6	28.4	46.5	52.5	not detected
Minerals, mg/100 g					
Na	26	15	25	29	20
K	165	93	156	170	125
Ca	18.2	10.4	17.2	19.8	13.8
Mg	11.1	6.3	10.5	12.0	8.4
Fe	0.49	0.29	0.46	0.54	0.38

All samples contain B vitamins, β-carotene and vitamin C, which are partially preserved after gentle heat treatment, as well as essential amino acids.

Obtained along the way in the production of jelly juice contains vitamins, micro- and macronutrients, irreplaceable acids.

The content of carbohydrates and vitamins B₁, B₂ is at the same level, the amount of proteins in the product is 0.48 %, which is 0.12 % less than in raw materials. Vitamin C decreases as a result of heat treatment at 15 mg/100 g of product. The amount of mineral substances is at the same level, except potassium, its content in the product is relatively larger (9 mg/100 g), and the remaining trace elements (Ca, Mg), except for Fe, vary slightly. The titrated acidity of the product is higher by 0.4 %. In general, the nutritional and biological value of juice from melon is higher due to dry substances, carbohydrates and protein raw materials.

Organoleptic indices of juice from melon indicate that the juice has a light-yellow color, in appearance it is a homogeneous mixture with a slight deposit on the bottom, there is an easy stratification, the taste is peculiar to melon, pleasant, sweet, without extraneous shades, the smell is pleasant, characteristic of melon, without discolouring shades and without foreign flavor, and the consistency is viscous.

As a criterion for assessing the quality of products from melon during storage, organoleptic indices were taken. Investigations of organoleptic properties have shown that for all types of products, the general orientation of the change in sensory indices, which is expressed in their decrease, is characteristic. In the initial period of storage, all the samples had the smell inherent in this species and a pleasant taste, under all modes it was tender, juicy, but gradually, as the consistency of the product changed, it acquired various shades uncharacteristic of the product.

Deterioration of taste qualities in juices becomes noticeable after 9 months. More stable at storage are jams and confitures from melon, deterioration of their quality indicators was observed by the end of 18 months. For jam (povidlo) 21 months.

The study of the storage of melon products showed that the storage temperature determines the flow of colloid-chemical and biochemical processes in them, and thus the quality of the products. The best products are stored at temperatures from 0 to 8 °C. In this case, sweet melon products for 15 months had a dense consistency, pleasant taste and smell, they have well preserved organoleptic properties. The further increase in the storage period promoted the development of undesirable phenomena in the samples. There is a decrease in water retention capacity (wrinkling of fruits, separation).

The fastest products were damaged at a temperature of 15 °C: they showed a rapid decrease in organoleptic properties after 3–12 months of storage.

The results of the study on the establishment of the maximum allowable shelf life at the optimum temperature range from 0 to 80 °C indicate that the maximum allowable shelf life is 9–12 months for juices, 18 months or more for sweet canned products.

Thus, at the end of this period, each type of melon product has some qualitative changes. Juice, after the expiration of the maximum allowable shelf life, a slight change in the overall pattern of color and sediment has appeared. At the jam the beginning of the crystallization of sugar, confiture and especially jam, the stratification was observed, the appearance of a layer of the liquid phase began and developed in the upper part. Significant changes in the chemical composition, nutritional and biological values of the products were not noted in the indicated time frames.

During an internship at the University of Storage technology Plovdiv (Bulgaria) experiments for the production of jams from local varieties of melons have been performed with the addition of high and low-esterified pectins. Melons of varieties “Italy” and “Galia” were used.

When preparing the pectin solution, the sample of pectin was mixed with sugar and, with gradual dosing and mixing at a high frequency of about 2000 rpm, was added to water at a temperature of 60 °C. After aging, pour into the jam a few minutes before the end of the heat treatment. Separately, a solution of citric acid was prepared in water with or without addition of CaCl₂. After the addition of all the components, the jam was kept at 90 °C for 2...3 minutes and poured into sterilized dishes, capped. All products are characterized by high organoleptic parameters, contains essential amino acids, vitamins B and C, β-carotene. The sugar content of jams produced in Bulgaria is less than in most of the products we offer. Products have the necessary consistency.

When pectin was extracted, the melon crust was crushed to a particle size of –5 mm and treated with a 0.5 % aqueous solution of acids at a temperature of 80 °C for 90 minutes, with a hydromodule equal to 5 and mixing at a speed of 120 rpm. After processing, the solution was isolated by vacuum filtration on a paper filter. The precipitate was washed with hot distilled water, the precipitation of pectic substances with calcium chloride and their purification with ethyl alcohol. The precipitate was separated on a vacuum filter, dried and weighed. Then, the degree of extraction of pectin from the raw material in percent was calculated as the ratio of the weight of extracted pectin to the pectin contained in the feed.

In order to extract the pectin from the crusts as much as possible, a hydrochloric acid solution of various concentrations was used as an extractant in further studies. The results of studying

the effect of extractant concentration on the extraction of pectin from raw materials at a temperature of 80 °C and hydromodule 5 are shown in **Fig. 6**. It follows from **Fig. 6** that the most intensive extraction increases in the first 60 minutes of mixing, in 90 minutes practically reaches its maximum at an acid concentration of more than 5 %, so increasing the concentration of more than 0.5 % is not advisable.

The growth of extraction of pectin at 0.25 percent acid continues throughout the duration of treatment for 150 minutes and does not reach the maximum value. On the basis of the data obtained, it can be concluded that the concentration of hydrochloric acid is 0.5 % optimal. The results of studying the effect of the hydromodule (ratio $x:m$) in hydrolysis-extraction are shown in **Fig. 7**. With an increase in the hydromodule from 3 to 10, an appreciable increase in the rate of the process is observed at the initial stage. By 60 minutes of treatment with hydromodules 5, 7, 10, most of the pectin is recovered, and by the 90th minute the extraction reaches its maximum value of 95..96 percent and is preserved at this level during further processing. With a hydromodule equal to 3, the process speed slows down considerably, which can be explained by a larger fraction of the boundary layer in the total volume of the system, a lower concentration gradient.

The size was changed stepwise, crushing the melon crust on sieves with holes of 1, 3, 5, 7, 10 mm. The treatment was carried out with hydrochloric acid with a concentration of 0.5 % at a temperature of 80 °C and a hydromodule equal to 5. A decrease in the extraction rate of pectin with increasing particle size is due to the fact that the value of the slow stage of pectin diffusion from the inner regions of the melon pieces to their surface increases. So when using particles with a size of 3..5 mm, the maximum possible extraction is achieved with 90 minutes of processing. For particles of less than 1 mm, the treatment time is reduced to 60 minutes, however, it is difficult to separate the extract. Larger particles require an increase in the duration of the process to 120..150 minutes.

The effect of temperature on the extraction of pectin was studied under the following conditions: particle size less than 5 mm, hydromodule 5, acid concentration 5 %. The temperature in the experiments was 60, 70, 80, and 90 degrees.

At temperatures of 60 and 70 degrees, the extraction increased with the increase in treatment time almost in direct dependence and in 150 minutes did not reach the maximum value. At 80 and 90 degrees the maximum extraction was achieved in 90 minutes of treatment, and at a temperature of 90 degrees 95 percent recovery of the component was noted after 60 minutes.

Increasing the extraction time at 90 degrees from 60 to 90 minutes results in an increase in recovery of about 5 %. However, 90 minutes of treatment at 80 degrees output extraction by a few tenths below, therefore, to determine the optimum temperature, economic calculations are needed, which can only be carried out on the basis of the results of consolidated tests.

Fig. 6. Dependence of extraction of pectin on the duration of treatment with hydrochloric acid with a concentration of 0.25; 0.5; 0.75; 1.0 % at a temperature of 80 °C and hydromodule 5

Fig. 7. Dependence of extraction of pectin on the duration of treatment with hydrochloric acid at a concentration of 0.5 % at a temperature of 80 °C and hydronic module 3, 5, 7, 10

Analyzing the obtained results of studies of the influence of the parameters of the process of processing melted crusts with acid solutions on the extraction of pectin, it can be concluded that the most acceptable conditions are: the concentration of hydrochloric acid is 0.5 % with the hydro module about 5 and the temperature of 80–90 degrees, the size of the pieces is 3...5 mm, the duration of 60...90 minutes [25–28]. To refine the data obtained, additional studies of the influence of the main technological factors on the extraction of pectin from melon crusts were carried out using the procedure for planning the experiment according to the plan of the full factor experiment 23. The duration of treatment of the crust with acid (as the factors influencing the output of pectin $y(\%)$, x_1 , min, acid concentration (x_2 , %) and temperature (x_3 , °C).

As a result, a regression equation is obtained that describes the dependence of extraction of pectin on the indicated parameters:

$$y=26.414+0.234x_1-4.418x_2+0.302x_3+0.324x_1x_2+0.386x_1x_3-0.0052x_1x_2x_3. \quad (2)$$

The calculated data obtained from the regression equation 20 correlate with the experimental results in the variation interval.

After extraction and drying, studies were conducted to establish the properties, composition and structure of pectin.

The main properties of pectin, above all, include the degree of esterification and the nucleus-forming ability. The main characteristics and properties of the obtained pectin with a degree of esterification of 67...69 % and the nucleus-forming capacity of more than 170 degrees of Tarr Baker, the strength of the jelly is about 460 mm Hg. meet the requirements of GOST and sanitary standards. After determining the optimal parameters of the technology of curing pectin and its properties, composition and structure, the dried pectin was aimed at studying the effect of storage regimes.

The southern regions of Republic of Kazakhstan are suitable for cultivation of melon group of fruits, melons and watermelons. Especially favorable conditions for their production are: South-Kazakhstan, Zhambyl and Kyzylorda regions. Namely, cultivated varieties with the highest taste and high yield. In these regions, the majority of areas are used for planting melons, the bulk of the harvest is collected in the republic. Melon is also grown in the Almaty region, but in less quantity and variety of varieties, favorable for climatic conditions are Mangistau and Atyrau regions.

The production of melons according to regions: South Kazakhstan (64 %), Zhambyl (15 %), Kyzylorda (6.4 %) and Almaty (5.4 %). More than 80 % of melons are grown in peasant and farm households.

Melon seeds are rich in protein substances and oil. They also contain galactan, glucose, gum, and resin. The seed protein consists of glutelin and globulin.

Waste of seeds after oil production – a valuable feed for livestock. About half of the extractive nitrogen is non-protein nitrogen and 15 % is amino acids (cystine, lysine, histidine, arginine, tryptophan), 50 % consisting of arginine. Quality of melons seeds oil is not inferior to the best varieties of provance oil.

Oil has pleasant smell, good taste, light yellow color. The relative density of the oil at 15 °C is 0.917–0.929; the refractive index at 20 °C is 1.4725; the solidification temperature is about –5 °C.

According to the data of the company FitoProduct [29] Melon oil has curative and preventive remedy abilities, which retains a large number of vitamins and biologically active substances.

Using melon oil in food gives the dishes a wonderful aroma and has a powerful positive effect on the organism.

In melons oil composition dominated polyunsaturated fatty acids, which regulate the level of lipemia, hemostasis activity, activate metabolic processes, affect the membrane formations of the central nervous system and the visual apparatus.

Unsaturated fatty acids 82 %: linolenic acid 1 % (Omega-3), linoleic acid 60 % (Omega-6), oleic acid 21 % (Omega-9). Saturated fatty acids 18 %: palmitic acid 10 %, stearic acid 8 %. Vitamins: A, E, beta-carotene. Mineral substances: zinc, etc. Caloric content of melon oil is 899 kcal.

In Republic of Kazakhstan, currently there is no production of melon oil, which is a raw material for the food industry and medicine, which is also used for the production of dietary supplements and cosmetics. In order to increase the profitability of the production of melon-based products, let's propose its complex processing, including the production of juices, jams and other similar products from pulp, pectin from crusts and melon seed oil from melon seeds.

At the first stage, studies were conducted with the most common melons in the Almaty region, Myrzachulskaya and Kolhoznitsa.

Melon seeds are yellow or cream colored, elongated-elliptical. The average length is 0.92 (Kolhoznitsa) and 1.4 (Myrzachulskaya), width 0.41 (Kolhoznitsa) and 0.59 (Myrzachulskaya), cm. the mass of the seeds was about 4.0–5.0 % of the mass of raw material taken for processing.

Commodity fraction of melon seeds with an initial humidity of 6–10 % was calibrated on a sieve with holes 5 mm in diameter. Two fractions were produced – a run-in fraction in an amount of about 80–85 % and a passing fraction in an amount of about 15–20 %. The converting fraction was sent for further processing, the passage was placed in a glass flask for intermediate storage and processed further as necessary according to the same scheme.

Results and analysis **Table 14** presents the general chemical composition of the core and the fruit shell of melon seeds of “Kolhoznitsa” and “Myrzachulskaya” varieties of the 2016 crop.

Analysis of the results of **Table 15** shows that in the fruit shell are concentrated fiber and nitrogen-free extractives, and the content of oil-bearing substances is insignificant, so it was advisable to try to apply the processing with the separation of the fruit shell.

Comparative results of oil extraction after IR processing of the core fraction and whole seeds are given in **Table 17**. Preparation of the core fraction was carried out as described above. Infrared treatment of whole seeds was carried out by irradiation at the plant SVS-200W for 120 seconds at a distance of 90 mm from the seed (the distance is chosen taking into account that the design of the unit allows covering the whole area of seeds with a given flux density of 900 W/m²).

For the melon variety “Kolhoznitsa” the core is 69.1 % of the weight of the whole seed, husk – 30.9 %. The melon of the Myrzachulskaya variety is 64.3 % and 35.7 %, respectively. If to calculate the output of oil from the core fraction to the output of whole seeds, it turns out that it will be lower than when whole seeds are squeezed out.

So for the melon of the type “Kolhoznitsa” 23.5 instead of 26.0, and for the variety “Myrzachulskaya” – 19.3 and 24.6. Thus, if to take into account only the output of oil, then it is not advisable to carry out expensive operations to separate the nucleus, so further studies on oil extrusion were carried out on whole seeds.

In the research were used seeds of characteristic varieties of Republic of Kazakhstan: Taisia, Zhansaya, Ethiopia, Prima, Altynochka, Kolkhoznitsa, Maiskaya, Muza, Iliyskaya, Honey. The melon seeds of these varieties are almost white, yellow or cream-colored, elongated-elliptical, 8.0 (Prim) length – 13.8 (Muse) and 4.2–5.8 mm wide, constitute 0.6–2.0 % of the weight of the fetus. The mass

of thousands of seeds varies from 41.0 (Honey) to 51.0 (Collective Farmer). The masses of the seed coat and nucleus are approximately equal. The average values of seeds are given in **Table 16**.

Table 14

General chemical composition of the core and the fruit shell of melon seeds

Index	“Kolhoznitsa” melons seeds		“Myrzachulskaya” melons seeds	
	Core	Fruit shell	Core	Fruit shell
Mass fraction, %: moisture and volatile substances	5.21	8.17	4.96	7.88
total protein in terms of absolutely dry matter	42.89	5.12	40.67	5.19
oil content in terms of oil equivalent	38.75	0.69	39.31	0.88
carbohydrates, including:				
cellulose	6.15	39.16	7.89	41.89
sucrose	0.67	0.59	0.66	0.52
ashes	4.15	2.42	4.12	2.14
nitrogen-free extractive matter	–	43.82	–	41.94

Table 15

Indicators of oil extraction

Index	«Kolhoznitsa»		«Myrzachulskaya»	
	Core fraction	Whole seeds	Core fraction	Whole seeds
Initial humidity, %	4.5	5.28	4.0	5.19
Mass fraction of moisture and volatile substances in oil, %	1.03±0.1	1.02±0.1	1.04±0.1	1.04±0.1
Output by weight of oil sample, %	34.0	26.0	30.0	24.6
Acid number, mg KOH/g	1.03±0.02	1.10±0.02	0.9±0.02	0.9±0.02
Peroxide number, mmol active oxygen/kg	2.05±0.04	2.10±0.04	1.90±0.04	1.97±0.04
Content:				
B-carotene, %	0.34±0.05	0.30±0.05	0.31±0.05	0.27±0.05
Vitamin E, mg/100 g	48.1±0.18	46.9±0.18	48.5±0.18	47.9±0.18

Chemical composition of seeds (% in terms of SW): water – 6.0–6.2; lipids – 25.0–26.5; protein ($N \times 6.25$) – 22.5–25.5; starch and soluble sugars – 10.0–11.0; pentosans – up to 8.0; cellulose – 20.0–21.4; ash – 2.5–3.0. The core contains up to 50 % oil, and in the husk – 0.5–0.6 %. Seeds also contain galactan, glucose, gum, and resin. The seed protein consists of glutelin and globulin.

The oil was squeezed from non-husked seeds on the DoLong electric screw press with screw heating up to 90 °C. The oil output, calculated as the ratio of the oil mass to the weight of the sample, is given in **Table 17**.

Comparison of the data in **Tables 16, 17** shows that the outcome of oil does not depend on the size or weight of the thousands of melon seeds, but is determined mainly by the oil content and permeability of the shell.

Table 16

Physical parameters of seeds

Type	Weight 1,000 seeds, g	Average-length, mm	Average-width, mm
Kolkhoznitsa	51.0	11.61	5.20
Muza	50.3	11.55	5.19
Altynochka	48.0	10.67	5.06
Maiskaya	48.0	12.11	5.28
Taisia	46.0	11.79	5.20
Ethiopia	44.5	11.24	4.92
Iliskaya	44.4	11.29	5.03
Zhansaya	42.0	11.69	5.10
Honey	41.0	11.78	5.18
Prima	32.0	9.66	5.44

Table 17
The oil output

Type	Humidity, %	Oil output, %
Kolkhoznitsa	5.28	26.0
Muza	4.15	22.5
Altynochka	5.19	24.6
Maiskaya	5.10	22.5
Taisia	5.23	19.0
Ethiopia	6.64	23.5
Iliskaya	5.38	23.5
Zhansaya	5.23	24.6
Honey	5.30	20.0
Prima	5.99	24.0

Oil samples after spinning are shown in **Fig. 8**.

Fig. 8. Oil sample of different melon types

The melon seed oil is edible, light yellow in color. Fatty acid composition of triacylglycerols of melon oil (% of total fatty acids): $C_{14:0}$ – 2, $C_{16:0}$ – 10–13, $C_{18:0}$ – 5–6, $C_{18:1}$ – 33–37, $C_{18:2}$ – 56–57, $C_{22:0}$ – 1.

Oil of pleasant smell, good taste, light yellow color. The relative density of the oil at 15 °C is 0.918–0.925; the refractive index at 20 °C is 1.359–1.479; the solidification temperature is about –5 °C. Melon oil is characterized by high (123–183 mg) iodine index and low (0.9–1.2 mg) – acidic.

Unsaturated fatty acids 82 %: linolenic acid 1 % (Omega-3), linoleic acid 60 % (Omega-6), oleic acid 21 % (Omega-9). Saturated fatty acids 18 %: palmitic acid 10 %, stearic acid 8 %. Vitamins: A, E, beta-carotene. Mineral substances: zinc, etc. Caloric content of Melon oil is 899 kcal.

Influence of the content of the fruit shell in the core fraction, as well as the processing of whole grains, on the parameters of melted oil, determining the degree of its oxidation, the most important indicator of the quality of vegetable oils was studied.

3. 2. Discussion

In this study, it is concluded that the melon variety is of great importance, as is the growing season. Melons of early-ripening varieties differ from late-ripening varieties, intervarietal features also affect the choice of the product produced. So there are melon varieties applicable for jams, marmalades, but not suitable for other products, because output is small, etc. There are also melon varieties that are not quite suitable even for the production of jams and jams, because the low acidity of fruits plays a role, when adding acid from outside, the taste and smell of products changes.

Melon fruits have an unpleasant odor during processing, to eliminate this, you need to have an extractor, but after heat treatment, the smell of melon is restored.

The difference of this study is in an integrated approach to the study of melon fruits in order to study varietal characteristics and recommendations for the production of products from melon fruits.

4. Conclusions

As a result of the research, geometric parameters of the eight varieties of the melon, most sale in Republic of Kazakhstan, have been determined, for the development of a universal crust separation. The physical and mechanical characteristics of various parts of the melon are determined. The melon density is 1.14–1.32 kg/m³, the adhesive stress for the pulp is 2.3–3.2 kPa, the coefficient of friction is 0.19–0.31, the specific cutting force is 2,386–2,485 N/m, the piercing force of the crust 3.22–33.87 N, depending on the diameter and angle of sharpening of the spikes of the conveyor, as well as the bulk modulus of elasticity at compression – 3,258–3,931 kPa. The mathematical dependences of the main mechanical characteristics of pulp and melon crust are determined. The obtained data were used in the development of technology and the apparatus for separating the crust and pulping the pulp used in the proposed technology.

The chemical composition of pulp, crust and seeds of the most common varieties of melon have been determined. The crust contains pectin in an amount of 1.18...1.67 % of the total mass. The proportion of protopectin in the total content of pectin substances is in the range of 75.37–96.25 %, which makes it possible to economically process melon crusts for pectin. Pulp and melon seeds contain vitamins and microelements, in seeds – unsaturated fatty acids.

Recipes of melon jams with the addition of pectin, juices based on melon are made. Optimum additions of pectin to products were established: for confiture it was about 10 g/kg, for jam 8 g/kg, for jam 5 g/kg. Acts of tasting and indicators of the biological value of products from melons enriched with pectin were obtained. Recommendations on storage regimes of products are determined.

Optimum parameters of extraction of pectin from crusts are determined: the concentration of hydrochloric acid is 0.5 % with the hydro-module about 5 and the temperature is 80–90 degrees, the size of the pieces is +3...–5 mm, the duration is 60...90 minutes. Pectin with a degree of esterification of 67...69 %, a stellate-forming capacity of more than 170 degrees of Tarr Baker, jelly strength of about 460 mm was obtained. gt; article, according to the obligatory normative indicators, which meets the requirements of GOST and sanitary norms. Conditions and terms of storage are established.

The technology of oil extraction is developed, including IR-processing, and squeezing of not melted melon seeds. According to the results of studies of 10 sorts of melon, the optimum mode of IR heat treatment of seeds was determined on the SVS-200W for 120 seconds at a distance of 90 mm from the seeds at a radiation flux density of 900 W/m². The squeezing of the unheel seeds does not have a significant effect on the quality of the oil. Conditions and terms of oil storage are determined.

Oil of pleasant smell, good taste, light yellow color. The relative density of the oil at 15 °C is 0.918–0.925; the refractive index at 20 °C – 1,359–1,479; is characterized by a low index (0.90–1.20 mg) of the acid number. Contains unsaturated fatty acids, mainly linoleic (Omega-6) and oleic (Omega-9) acids in different ratios in grades, saturated fatty acids: palmitic (50 %), stearic and pentadecanoic acids of 25 % each. Vitamins: A, E, beta-carotene. Mineral substances: zinc, etc. Caloric value of oil is 899 kcal.

The tests of the complex melon processing technology to produce jam, juice, pectin and oil have confirmed its effectiveness. The technology is recommended for the implementation of the Zarechny settlement in the Almaty region after the development of the commercial proposal.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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